

An AI-Based Adaptive Headlight Control System Integrating YOLO, LiDAR, and V2V Communication

Ahmed Youssef Alsayed, Aya Sayed Ahmed, Abdallah Hossam Elden Ramzy, Ahmed Mostafa Mohamed, Omar Mohamed Abdel Razek

Dr. Hayam A. Abdelhameed

ABSTRACT

High-beam glare during nighttime driving poses a significant risk, especially on rural roads where visibility is limited. Many drivers fail to properly dim their high beams when approaching other vehicles, which can cause dangerous temporary visual impairment. To address this issue, this paper presents the design and implementation of an AI-driven adaptive headlight control system. The system combines real-time object detection using a YOLOv8 model with LiDAR-based distance sensing and a vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) communication module. The LiDAR and camera operate in parallel using multi-threading, allowing synchronized perception of the driving environment. Additionally, an ESP32-based V2V system with a GY-271 magnetometer transmits directional data to detect oncoming vehicles based on heading comparison. Once both object detection and directional alignment are verified, the system adjusts headlight intensity using PWM control to reduce glare. The proposed system is implemented on a Raspberry Pi 4 platform and tested under different lighting and traffic conditions to verify performance, responsiveness, and safety enhancement.

Keywords

Adaptive Headlight System, Smart Vehicles, YOLOv8, Object Detection, Roboflow Dataset, LiDAR, V2V Communication, GY-271 Magnetometer, Raspberry Pi 4, ESP32, MQTT Protocol, RSSI.

I. INTRODUCTION

Driving at night presents significant challenges due to reduced visibility, making it more difficult for drivers to perceive obstacles, road signs, and other vehicles. To compensate for the lack of natural light, vehicles are equipped with high-beam headlights, which provide greater illumination for the driver. However, the excessive brightness of high beams can cause glare, temporarily impairing the vision of other drivers, increasing the risk of collisions. This challenge is especially critical on two-lane roads and highways where oncoming traffic is directly exposed to the intense light.

Recent studies have highlighted the growing concern over headlight glare. A survey conducted by the RAC [2023] found that 89% of drivers believe some vehicle headlights are too bright, with 91% reporting that they have been dazzled by oncoming headlights. This glare can lead to discomfort and temporary vision impairment, increasing the risk of accidents [1].

This paper presents the design of an intelligent headlight control system that leverages deep learning and multi-sensor fusion to adaptively manage headlight intensity and direction in real-time. The system utilizes a Raspberry Pi 4 with a NoIR camera module for capturing live video frames, and a lightweight YOLOv8 object detection model to identify vehicles and pedestrians on the road. Additionally, LiDAR provides accurate distance measurements, while a V2V communication module using ESP32 and GY-271 magnetometers exchange heading data with nearby vehicles. By integrating data from both the vision system and V2V direction analysis using multi-threaded processing, the proposed system dynamically adjusts headlight brightness through PWM control, reducing glare for oncoming traffic and enhancing safety during nighttime driving.

II. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the architecture, operation, and implementation steps of the proposed smart headlight control system, focusing on the object detection pipeline, LiDAR-based distance measurement, and V2V integration via RSSI and GY-271 magnetometer.

a. Object Detection

The system uses a lightweight deep learning model (YOLOv8) running on a Raspberry Pi 4 to perform real-time object detection from video input captured by the Raspberry Pi Camera Module 3 NoIR. YOLOv8 was chosen for its high inference speed and accuracy in detecting multiple classes

simultaneously. The input frame is divided into grid cells, with each grid predicting object probabilities and bounding boxes [2].

A custom dataset created and trained using Roboflow includes seven classes: Car, Person, Traffic Light, Truck, Bicycle, Speed Limit 30, and Stop Sign [3]:

Fig 1: YOLO Methodology

- **Vehicles:** Trigger LED headlight dimming in the corresponding frame section.
- **Pedestrians:** Alert the driver and reduce intensity in the pedestrian’s direction.
- **Traffic Signs:** Display a message or symbol to notify the driver.

Instead of manually dividing the frame into vertical regions, the object detection is combined with LiDAR distance filtering and to ensure that dimming occurs only when objects are within range and pose a potential risk. This integrated approach improves detection reliability and minimizes false responses due to irrelevant objects in the background.

Fig 2: Overview of the system architecture integrating YOLOv8, LiDAR, V2V communication, and PWM-based headlight control.

b. LiDAR Integration and Angular Filtering

A 360° OKdo LiDAR HAT (LD06_LD) is connected to the Raspberry Pi via UART for continuous real-time distance scanning. To eliminate detecting irrelevant objects (e.g., from the sides or rear), the system filters measurements to focus only on a defined angular range directly in front of the vehicle [4].

Objects detected within an angular range of 40°–80° and within a predefined proximity distance of 0.2 meters are used to trigger dimming actions. This angular filtering ensures the system reacts only to objects that may cause headlight glare.

c. V2V Communication using RSSI and GY-271

To complement visual and distance-based detection, the system incorporates a V2V communication layer using ESP32 microcontrollers. Each vehicle is equipped with a GY-271 digital compass module [5] to determine heading, and the ESP32 publishes heading data over MQTT via a Raspberry Pi-hosted Wi-Fi access point [6].

Simultaneously, RSSI (Received Signal Strength Indicator) is monitored to estimate the relative distance between vehicles. A vehicle is classified as approaching if the following conditions are met:

- RSSI signal strength is increasing (closer proximity)
- Heading difference between the two vehicles is $\sim 180^\circ \pm 45^\circ$ (opposite directions)

When both conditions are met, the system reduces headlight brightness to prevent glare. A centralized control module on the Raspberry Pi is responsible for managing headlight dimming decisions, taking inputs from both LiDAR + Camera fusion and V2V logic.

This integration ensures robust, accurate decision-making even in edge cases, improving overall system performance in real-world nighttime driving.

III. RESULTS

The proposed system was fully implemented and tested in real-world scenarios to validate the performance of object detection, LiDAR-based distance filtering, and V2V-based decision-making. The system's effectiveness was evaluated under various conditions, including object proximity, direction alignment, and ambient lighting.

a. YOLO Model Performance

YOLOv8 was trained using a custom Roboflow dataset that includes classes such as vehicles, pedestrians, and traffic signs. The model was evaluated across different sizes, with YOLOv8-*Nano* offering the best balance between accuracy and inference speed on the Raspberry Pi 4.

Table 1: YOLOv8 Model Parameters and Performance

Size	No. of Epochs	Data Size	Accuracy	Splitting Ratio
Nano	67	3618	81.8%	Train: 70% Validation: 20% Test: 10%
Small			82.3%	

A confusion matrix was generated to evaluate classification accuracy for each class. The loss curves for training and validation showed stable convergence across bounding box regression (`box_loss`), class confidence (`cls_loss`), and focal loss (`df_loss`).

Fig 3: Sample images from the collected dataset showing various urban driving scenes captured for training the object detection model

b. LiDAR Testing

The 360° LiDAR sensor (OKdo LD06_LD) was configured to focus only on a specified angular window (40°–80°) representing the front-facing region. This angular selection corresponds to the direction in which oncoming vehicles are most likely to appear relative to the vehicle’s heading, thereby reducing unnecessary processing and eliminating detections from irrelevant directions (e.g., roadside objects or parked vehicles). When an object—such as a vehicle or pedestrian—is detected by both the LiDAR (within the distance threshold) and the YOLOv8 camera system (within the image frame), the two systems work in tandem to confirm the object’s presence and trigger headlight dimming. This dual detection approach ensures high accuracy and avoids false positives caused by irrelevant objects.

Distance-based filtering was applied to trigger headlight dimming only when objects are detected within a threshold distance of 0.2 meters, simulating realistic urban driving scenarios where vehicles or pedestrians appear suddenly. This close-range detection threshold ensures that the system reacts only when necessary, minimizing distraction and energy waste. The results showed high stability, low latency, and consistent responsiveness across varying lighting and environmental conditions, supporting the system’s suitability for real-time embedded automotive applications.

c. V2V Communication Validation

The V2V approach provides an additional layer of verification. The V2V module, implemented using ESP32 microcontrollers and GY-271 digital compass modules, successfully transmitted heading data over MQTT through a

Raspberry Pi configured as a local access point. Each vehicle continuously broadcast its orientation, and real-time comparison of heading angles enabled the detection of oncoming vehicles when the relative angle fell within $180^\circ \pm 45^\circ$, indicating opposite directions. This directional awareness is crucial to ensure the system reacts only to vehicles that pose a potential glare risk.

In parallel, RSSI (Received Signal Strength Indicator) values were monitored to estimate the relative distance between vehicles. To enhance reliability, a sliding average was applied to filter out sudden spikes and noise in the signal. A consistent increase in RSSI levels was found to strongly correlate with vehicle approach, reinforcing the system's ability to interpret proximity trends in dynamic environments. This dual-condition approach—direction + distance—ensures that headlight dimming is only triggered in relevant scenarios, reducing false positives and optimizing system efficiency under real-world operating conditions.

d. Integration Testing

The complete system was tested with integrated logic using multi-threading. Real-time object detection, LiDAR input, and V2V heading/RSSI were synchronized to trigger dimming actions only when all conditions were met. The PWM-controlled headlight responded instantly, adjusting brightness according to threat level.

Fig 4: Confusion matrix

Fig 5: YOLOv8 training and evaluation curves showing loss components and detection metrics (precision, recall, mAP) across epochs.

Fig 6: Detection results showing predicted bounding boxes using YOLOv8

(a)

(b)

Fig 7: Testing the prototype of the adaptive headlight system when: (a) turning ON all LEDs at full brightness before object detection, (b) dimming LEDs by 50% after detecting an oncoming vehicle 0.2 meters away.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the development of a smart adaptive headlight control system aimed at improving safety during nighttime driving. The proposed system integrates real-time object detection using YOLOv8, proximity sensing via a 360° LiDAR sensor, and direction estimation through a V2V communication module based on RSSI and GY-271 compass data. Testing demonstrated that the system effectively dims the headlights when both object presence and opposing vehicle direction are confirmed, minimizing glare without compromising the driver's visibility. The system operates using cost-effective and widely available hardware, making it suitable for deployment in low-resource environments. Compared to high-end commercial systems, the proposed solution is more cost-effective, scalable, and easier to integrate into standard vehicles while maintaining robust performance in dynamic environments.

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